

**METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING THE CREATIVE COMPETENCIES OF
PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS (BASED ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE MOTHER
TONGUE AND READING LITERACY)****Navoiy University of Innovations, Primary Education Teacher:****Gulrux Jabborova**

Annotation: The primary education system plays an important role in forming students' initial knowledge and skills. Mother tongue and reading literacy lessons hold special significance in this process, as they help develop students' speech and thinking abilities. At the same time, developing the creative competencies of primary school teachers is a crucial factor in shaping students' independent thinking and creativity..

Keywords: Creative competence, methodology, didactic game, 4K model, project-based approach, metacognitive competence.

Аннотация: Система начального образования играет важную роль в формировании первоначальных знаний и навыков учащихся. Особое значение в этом процессе имеют занятия по родному языку и чтению, способствующие развитию навыков говорения и мышления учащихся.

В то же время развитие творческих компетенций учителей начальной школы является важным фактором развития самостоятельного мышления и креативности учащихся.

Ключевые слова: Творческая компетентность, методология, дидактическая игра, модель 4К, проектный подход, метакогнитивная компетентность.

Abstract: The primary education system plays an important role in the formation of students' foundational knowledge and skills. Lessons in the mother tongue and reading literacy are particularly important in this process, as they help develop students' speaking and thinking skills. At the same time, the development of primary school teachers' creative competencies is a key factor in fostering students' independent thinking and creativity.

Keywords: Creative competence, methodology, didactic game, 4K model, project-based approach, metacognitive competence.

In the process of learning the mother tongue, the materials used in schools play a special role in shaping students' scientific worldview. The authenticity, ideological direction, and artistic expression of these materials impact students' cognitive activity and emotions, broaden their knowledge of the surrounding world, stimulate interest in the language and its native speakers,

contribute to their overall development, and influence the formation of their personal qualities and worldview.

In recent years, the requirements for the content of school mother tongue textbooks and teacher guides have significantly increased.

The main criteria for these materials include the educational value of texts and individual sentences, lexical-stylistic clarity, diversity of topics, connection to various aspects of life, ideological and thematic orientation of texts, and their suitability for young learners.

Meeting such requirements involves not only developing the main types of speech activities in primary school students, but also addressing the following important tasks:

Firstly, the content of mother tongue education in primary grades includes knowledge about the sound structure of the Uzbek language and how sounds are represented in written form, word changes and sentence structure, word morphology and formation, lexical-semantic groups, spelling rules, and punctuation usage. This knowledge supports the development of students' speech skills.

The content and methodology of teaching the mother tongue should help students acquire a solid foundation of knowledge, skills, and competencies as required by the curriculum. The main goal of mother tongue education is to develop students' communicative competence—enabling them to think, understand others' ideas, and express their own thoughts clearly and correctly both orally and in writing. It also includes developing grammatical knowledge (phonetics, lexicology, word structure, word formation, morphology, syntax, spelling, punctuation, speech styles, and stylistic concepts) and forming linguistic competencies so that students can correctly and fluently express what they read, see, and hear.

The curriculum for the mother tongue subject is developed based on the requirements of the State Educational Standard, which focuses on shaping students' competencies. It aims to develop subject-specific communicative and linguistic competencies, as well as elements of key competencies in students.

In primary education, ensuring literacy and forming adherence to literary norms in both oral and written speech are essential. In specialized public education institutions where the mother tongue is studied in depth from grades 1 to 4, the teaching process has been improved to enhance the quality and effectiveness of education and to further nurture students' abilities and talents.

The curriculum has been adapted to a competency-based approach. For example, at the A1 level, the total annual instructional time is 608 hours, while at the A1+ level, it is 680 hours.

This research analyzes various methodological approaches aimed at developing the creative competencies of primary school teachers. In particular, methods focused on enhancing students' creativity in reading literacy and native language lessons were examined. In addition, opportunities for developing students' reading skills through modern pedagogical technologies and interactive methods were explored.

Findings

The following methodological approaches are considered effective for developing the creative competencies of primary school teachers:

Use of game-based technologies: Didactic games such as "Mysterious Syllables" and "Think Quickly" can enhance students' creativity.

Application of the 4K model: Using the 4K model, which develops logical thinking, helps improve students' critical thinking skills.

Implementation of a project-based approach: This method proves effective in improving students' creative abilities.

Development of metacognitive competencies: The methodology for shaping creativity and metacognitive competencies through reading literacy helps students develop independent and critical thinking skills.

The use of modern pedagogical technologies and interactive methods plays a significant role in developing the creative competencies of primary school teachers. Game-based technologies, the 4K model, the project-based approach, and methods for developing metacognitive competencies help boost students' creativity. At the same time, it is important for teachers to continuously improve their own creative competencies, which contributes to the overall effectiveness of the educational process.

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